

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Influence of School Environment on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study focused on examining the influence of school environment on the academic performance of secondary school students in Calabar. The study specifically sought to analyse the extent to which location and physical facilities determines academic performance of students. Data for the study were obtained through field surveys including questionnaire administration. A total of 200 copies of questionnaire were distributed in the sampled schools. However, students were the target population of the study. The variables that were used in measuring location were noise, ventilation and travelling distance from home to schools. Variables for physical facilities were libraries, science laboratories, adequacy of classrooms and ICT/computer laboratories. It was observed in the study that majority of the schools were located in considerably far distances and the environs where schools are located are susceptible to noise and pollution. It was also noted that majority of the students were undertaking studies in poorly ventilated classrooms. Furthermore, the study observed that physical facilities such as libraries and laboratories were poorly equipped, classrooms were inadequate and ICT/computer laboratories were not properly equipped. All of these pose threats to the academic performance of students. For instance, it was observed that majority of the students perform low academically. Holistically, it is difficult for student to attain academic goals as well as perform academically well in school environments that are uncondusive and lack the necessary physical facilities. Based on the study findings, it was concluded that schools be located in places that are not prone to atmospheric and noise pollution. Equally, there is need to ensure that schools structures are designed in such a way that ventilation will be adequate was stressed. Finally, facilities such as libraries, science and computer laboratories should be equipped appropriately.

Keywords: Laboratories; libraries; location; physical facilities; traveling distance

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1.Introduction

Education is a veritable tool for national development. It is regarded as the bedrock of the nation and plays it an indispensable role in national integration. Due to its importance, the National Policy spelt out that education is an instrument for social change, development and sustainability. Therefore, for a nation to be revolutionized, the education of its people has to be given priority since education paves way for civilization and provides a sense of belonging to learners in the society. From the forgoing, it is clear that everyone deserve to be educated thus, access to good quality education is a fundamental human right (Emmet and Eur, 2011).

With the assertion that education is a fundamental right, it is important to ensure that the school environment is regulated in such a way that it will promote academic performance and achievement by learners. This is because the academic performance of students in the school is largely tied to school environmental factors and teaching styles (Chetty, Handayani, Sahabudin, Ali, Hamzah, Rahman and Kasim, 2019), student personnel management, the quality/quantity of teachers (Nwogu and Esobhawan, 2014; Maphoso and Mahlo, 2015; Aliyu and Ali, 2021) as well as the school environment (Chukwuemeka, 2013; Nsa, Offiong, Udo and Ikot, 2014). Basically, school environment provides the opportunity for training, the needed resources and the necessary assistance in the establishment and